

SIMULATION OF DENSITY BASED TRAFFIC LIGHT CONTROL USING RF TRANSCEIVER

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Abstract— The goal of this work is to build a density-based dynamic traffic signal system in which the signal timing changes automatically dependent on the traffic density at every given intersection. Because traffic congestion is a major issue in most cities across the world, it is time to transition from a human or fixed timer system to an automated system with decision-making capabilities. The current traffic signaling system is based on a predetermined time schedule, which might be inefficient if one lane is open longer than the others. We created a framework for an intelligent traffic control system to solve this challenge. Higher traffic density on one side of the intersection may necessitate a longer green time than the regular permitted time. As a result, we suggest a methodology in which the green light and red-light time periods are given based on the density of traffic present at the time. PIR is used to do this (Proximity Infrared sensors). The microcontroller is used to allocate the glowing period of green light after the density has been computed (Arduino). The sensors on the roadside will detect the presence of vehicles and communicate the information to the microcontroller (Arduino), which will determine how long a flank will remain open or when the signal lights will change.

Keywords-In this paper include density-based traffic control, infrared sensors, RF transmitter & receiver, and microcontroller-based algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

God's most intelligent creation is the human being. Humans are continuously coming up with new innovations to make living easier. With new wings of hope, people are beginning to raise their standard of life from the comfort of their own homes. This could be one of the reasons why road traffic is becoming increasingly congested. As a result, two major concerns have arisen. If there is no traffic, you will be compelled to wait in a square measure. Inadequate traffic management leads to massive traffic congestion and other issues. The following is a description of mounted management. When it comes to traffic, we have a tendency to prioritise traffic based on programming that is already in place among the systems, rather than density. We prefer to construct a bearing system that relies on density to maintain traffic control to

overcome the drawbacks of a complex and rapid traffic signal system. The concept is called an intelligent traffic congestion management system based on density. An intelligent traffic congestion management system based on density is a technology that can adjust itself to keep up with the quantity of cars, or density. With the help of IR sensors, we're developing a traditional control system, an associate degree intelligent traffic congestion control system. The IR sensing section consists of an infrared transmitter and a receiver. On either side of the lane, these infrared transmitters and receivers will be installed at a preset distance. The infrared function detects the vehicle as it goes along the road and transmits the information to the microcontroller. The microprocessor can keep track of how many there are and alter the LED's flashing time to correlate to the number of vehicles and their density. If the density is higher, LEDs will shine for longer, and if the density is lower, LEDs will shine for shorter. The main advantage of this method is that it reduces vehicle wait times. Because we all recognize that time is our most valuable asset these days, most drivers disregard traffic restrictions in order to arrive at their destination on time. Violations of traffic regulations are committed in order to attend for a prolonged amount of time regardless of whether or not traffic is accessible. As a result, the suggested method has a good chance of reducing people's issues while also lowering the number of occurrences that is happening on a regular basis.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

Currently, traffic cops use a system of traffic signs, hand signals, and markings to clean up the roads. Stop signs, for example, have a red institution and are polygonally worked; every vehicle control management widget is obligated by degrees of structure and use; Stop signs, for example, are shaped like a violin and have a red institution. Create templates to communicate with the driver so that the sign in the driver's field of view is readily and methodically understood. This assertion and the selection of the optimal technique of operation are aided by the standard use of colours and shapes. In this situation, traffic signals are being attacked in different ways, such as with a set time delay, which maintains a specific timeframe when dynamically changing from one sign to another, causing undesirable and unnecessary

mayhem on one route while keeping others empty. The methods we propose track the amount of traffic on certain routes and offer real-time data, allowing us to alter the sign detecting composition.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Infrared sensors are crucial in our system for sensing traffic density in all lanes. For each lane, one IR detector must be put; these sensors will always detect vehicles on that route. These sensors are coupled to an RF Transmitter, and the data sent by the RF Transmitter is received by an RF receiver coupled to a microcontroller. Based on the results of these sensors, the microcontroller detects and clears traffic. We usually propose a gadget that uses inexpensive electronic components such as a light-emitting diode as a signal indicator to alleviate traffic congestion. IR sensors were used to calculate vehicle density, and a microcontroller was used to calculate the amount of time spent waiting for a traffic light.

IV. SYSTEM PROTOTYPE

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Proposed System

V. COMPONENT DESCRIPTION

A. Power Supply

To address the power requirements of the hardware of the intelligent traffic signal system, a +5V supply with respect to GND has been devised. These circuits employed TTL logic levels ranging from 0V to 5V. It has a 0V to 9V power supply that converts 220V AC to 9V AC. The bridge rectifier converts the 9V to 9V2 DC. After that, it's filtered by a 1000uF capacitance before being regulated by a 7805 to get to +5V. To separate the +5V output voltage from noise, further 220uF capacitance filtering is employed.

B. Arduino nano

It's a compact, dependable, and robust open-source microcontroller that can be programmed, reprogrammed, and erased at any moment. The Arduino platform was created in 2005 to provide amateurs, students, and professionals with a low-cost and convenient means to build computers that move in response to their surroundings utilizing sensors and actuators. Designed and programmed electronic gadgets using a free and open-source computer platform. It may also operate as a mini-computer, accepting inputs and controlling outputs for a range of natural philosophy devices, similar to other microcontrollers. It also uses multiple Arduino shields to send and receive wireless data, which are detailed in this paper.

C. Infra-red Sensors

Infrared sensors are crucial in our system for sensing traffic density in all lanes. They're installed on both sides of the road and connect with the microcontroller using an RF receiver and transmitter module. With the help of the sensors' output, the microcontroller detects traffic and controls it. IR sensors are connected to the microcontroller. If there is traffic on the lane, the detector's output changes to logic one; otherwise, it changes to logic zero. The microcontroller increases the glow time of the go signal of the appropriate junction to a significantly greater value based on the results of the IR sensors logics. As a result, as the type of density increases, the go signal glows for longer.

Figure 2 : IR Sensor

D. Radio Frequency Transmitter and Receiver

A radio frequency transmitter and receiver module will be used inside the circuit to incorporate wireless communication for this project. The output of the IR sensor is delivered to the microcontroller with the help of this module.

Figure 3 : RF Transceiver

E. Light Emitting Diode

As a light indicator, two LEDs, i.e. stop and go signals, are used.

Figure 4 : LED

VI. FLOW CHART

Figure 5: Flow Chart of the Proposed System

VII. SIMULATION

Figure 5: Simulated Circuit Diagram of the Proposed System

VIII. RESULT

As a result of the research, an intelligent density-based traffic control system was successfully implemented. In this prototype, which is situated on opposite sides of roadways, we employ an infrared transmitter and receiver to measure traffic density. The infrared sensor detects the vehicle and transmits the data to the microcontroller using an RF transmitter and receiver. After that, the microcontroller makes a judgement and assigns the signal to it.

XI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we focused on the problem of traffic congestion in densely populated places. This device can be used to resolve traffic-related difficulties such as traffic congestion, which causes an excessive latency wait for cars to come to a complete stop, emergency vehicles, or forcibly passing, and so on. By employing this device design, we intend to lessen the risk of unduly crowded traffic caused by traffic signals. The microprocessor decides whether the lane should have a blinking traffic light based on the density, or the amount of vehicles passing through it.

IX. REFERENCES

- [1] Shruthi K R and Vinod Ha K proposed this in Priority Based Traffic Lights Controller Using Wireless Sensor Networks. (2012).
- [2] Image analysis will also help to alleviate traffic flow issues to a larger degree. Dangi, Amol Parab, Vikram-aditya Kshitij Pawar, and S. Rathod discuss this in Image Processing Based Intelligent Traffic Controller. (2012).
- [3] Francis, Arun & Arulselvan, M. & Elangkumaran, P. & Keerthivarman, S. & Kumar, J.. (2019). Object detection using ultrasonic sensor. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*. 8. 207-209.
- [4] Arun Francis G., Lexmitha S., Aruna Devi N., Swathika C. K., "Embedded System based Smart Automation for Elderly and Disabled People", *Annals of RSCB*, pp. 9909–9917, Apr. 2021.
- [5] Arun Francis G., Ashok Kumar M., Cyril Silvester A. K., Kamaleshwaran A. P., Kumaravel B., "Pulsed Electric Field based Vegetable Fresher", *Annals of RSCB*, pp. 9918–9926, Apr. 2021.
- [6] Arun Francis G., Kanishya A., Lalithambiga M., Niveka S., Nivedha E., "Density based Traffic Light Control Using Retransmitted and Receiver", *Annals of RSCB*, pp. 9895–9901, Apr. 2021.
- [7] Arun Francis G., Chandru L., Arun Kumar B., Nithesh Kumar R., Narendran S., "Charging Time Control Using Arduino", *Annals of RSCB*, pp. 9886–9894, Apr. 2021.
- [8] Arun Francis G., Mr. S. Manikandan, Sundar V., Gowtham E., "Home Automation Using Iot", *Annals of RSCB*, pp. 9902–9908, Apr. 2021.
- [9] Y. Neelaveni and G. A. Francis, "Magneto-electric dipole array with optimized antenna parameters," 2015 Online International Conference on Green Engineering and Technologies (IC-GET), Coimbatore, India, 2015, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/GET.2015.7453855.
- [10] M. A. Kumar and G. A. Francis, "Survey on various advanced technique for cache optimization methods for risc based system architecture," 2017 4th International Conference on Electronics and Communication Systems (ICECS), Coimbatore, India, 2017, pp. 195-200, doi: 10.1109/ECS.2017.8067868.
- [11] Francis, Arun. (2020). IoT Based Vehicle Emission Monitoring System. 8. 410-412.
- [12] Francis, Arun & Wilfred, M.W. & Sekar, R.. (2019). Health monitoring with alcohol detection and ignition control system using iot. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*. 8. 203-206.
- [13] Vignesh M, Kavin T P, A. F. G. G. C. R. K. S. (2020). Accident Detection and Alerting System Using GPS & GSM. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(3), 3598 - 3601. Retrieved from <http://sersc.org/journals/index.php/IJAST/article/view/5037>
- [14] Francis, Arun. (2020). Home Automation Chat Bot using IOT. *Waffen-und Kostumkunde*. 11. 92-96.
- [15] Arun Francis G, Dharani S K, Manikandan P, Monica RJ and Vaishahi S K, "IOT Based Accident Identification and Alerting System", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, vol.118, No.20, pp.547-551, 2018.
- [16] Mr.G.Arun Francis, Dr.P.Karthigaikumar, Mr.G.Arun Kumar (2020) FACE RECOGNITION SYSTEM FOR VISUALLY IMPAIRED PEOPLE. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7 (17), 2760-2764. doi:10.31838/jcr.07.17.345
- [17] [11] S.Manikandan, T.Karthik, and G.Arun Francis, "Vector Monitoring Concurrent BIST Architecture using Modified SRAM Cells", *International journal of science and advance research in technology*, Vol. 1 No.9 ,pp.14-17, Sep 2015.
- [18] [12] Koushik Mandal, Arindam fractional monetary unit, Abhijnan Chakraborty, and Siuli Roy used Active RFID and GSM technologies to track and quantify road traffic congestion monitoring system (2011).